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WIND IN MY BACKYARD

WIMBY

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Abstract

The WIMBY Wind Power Assessment Tool is an API that estimates the potential of wind farms in Europe. The API considers wind resources, wind farm boundaries, and user-provided turbine specifications for any European region. Currently, the tool is designed to optimise the annual energy production of the wind farm by utilising the TOPFARM integrated wind farm model. This report provides a comprehensive description of the WIMBY Wind Power Assessment Tool and its development process. It also outlines the processing of exclusion zones and the LCOE model developed at DTU Wind.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Abstract	4
1 INTRODUCTION	10
2 DATA	12
2.1 Wind resources data	12
2.2 Wind turbine data	13
2.3 Exclusion zones	13
3 MODELS	20
3.1 TOPFARM optimization	20
3.2 Levelized Cost of Energy model	24
3.3 Grid connection modelling	31
4 The WIMBY API	36
4.1 The WIMBY Wind Power Tool	36
4.2 Impact Models	38
5 CONCLUSIONS	40
REFERENCES	41

LIST OF FIGURES

1.1	Initial proposed concept of the WIMBY Wind Power API. . . .	10
2.1	Illustration of the DEM processing.	15
2.2	Example of the shipping lanes in the Danish Baltic Sea. . . .	19
3.1	Simulation results from the grid sweep optimization performed with the <i>smart-start</i> algorithm for the case of 50 wind turbines.	23
3.2	Composition and cost of each stage in the whole life cycle of the wind farm.	25
3.3	Hierarchy of the ORC model with all its components.	26
3.4	Visualisation of the path from a random wind farm in Bulgaria to its nearest substation.	35
3.5	Visualisation of the elevation from a random wind farm in Bulgaria to its nearest substation.	35
4.1	Flow diagram of the main components of the WIMBY wind power tool.	37
4.2	Clipping to the exclusion zones.	38

LIST OF TABLES

2.1	Datasets and their sources used as Hard constraints.	14
2.2	OSM tags for different WIMBY infrastructure categories.	17
3.1	Grid sweep parameters chosen for the smart-start algorithm	22
3.2	Single Circuit AC exploratory costs across various European countries at different voltage levels.	34

ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
AEP	Annual Energy Production
AGL	Above Ground Level
API	Application Programming Interface
CAPEX	Capital Expenses
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
EZ	Exclusion Zone
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPKG	GeoPackage
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Energy
NEWA	New European Wind Atlas
NetCDF	network Common Data Form
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
ORC	Open-source Region-specific LCOE
OPEX	Operating Expenses
OSM	Open Street Map
PyWake	DTU Python Wake Model
NEWA	New European Wind Atlas
REST	REpresentational State Transfer
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the WIMBY Wind Power API, which integrates wind resources, wind farm boundaries, and turbine specifications to assess the energy potential of wind farms across Europe. The tool combines models developed by DTU, which were previously standalone, to produce an optimised wind farm layout based on openly available datasets and user-provided configurations.

The WIMBY Wind Power API is designed to be deployed on a web server. It offers an API interface for calculating the locations of turbines within a user-specified wind farm boundary. Users provide a location of interest (e.g., a polygon) along with the necessary wind farm design criteria (number and type of turbines). The optimisation tool runs and return the locations of the wind turbines to maximise the wind farm's energy production. The result includes the geographic locations of each turbine and the AEP for the entire wind farm.

The prototype WIMBY Wind Power API has been delivered on time. The noise and shadow flicker models are already integrated into the WIMBY API. Debugging, performance optimization and integration of the additional models being developed by other partners will continue until the WIMBY interactive map (D5.2) is delivered.

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the objectives of the WIMBY project is to Understand and find ways to value the cumulative impacts of onshore and offshore wind power on society in Europe. This will be done by assessing impacts on local communities and other sectors and addressing issues concerning governance, regulations, health impacts and intangibles, such as scenery or landscape, in a spatially explicit way.

To achieve this objective, we developed the WIMBY Wind Power API, which combines wind resources, wind farm boundaries, and turbine specs to provide a wind farm layout optimised for energy production in any region of Europe and additional information about the wind farm’s impacts. Figure 1.1 shows a schematic diagram of the initial concept of the tool at the time the project began. The actual implementation (see chapter 4) is an adaptation of the original concept. There are differences in individual models and linkages, and additional connections have been made downstream of the wind farm layout.

Figure 1.1: Initial proposed concept of the WIMBY Wind Power API. Solid lines and boxes show existing connections, models, and databases; dashed lines and boxes show those to be developed throughout the project.

This deliverable is divided as follows: Section 2 describes the data used, including wind resources and exclusion zones and their pre-processing. Section 3 describes the models used, including the overall tool architecture and the new cost model. Section 4 presents the application of these models.

2 DATA

The WIMBY Wind Power API uses data from various sources. Data on wind resources (Section 2.1) are used to compute the AEP of a wind farm, given the wind turbine characteristics (Section 2.2). The area where wind turbines can be built is determined based on exclusion zones (Section 2.3). These three types of data are detailed below.

2.1 Wind resources data

Wind resource data for the tool comes from the New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) database, described in WIMBY deliverable D1.2 [1]. The particular data used is version 2 of the NEWA microscale database [2], which represents a 10-year average from (2014–2023)¹. The procedure and improvements over V1 are detailed in WIMBY report D1.2.[1]. The data are provided on a grid spacing of 50 m × 50 m and 3 vertical levels at 50, 100 and 200 m AGL. The variables wind direction frequency f and the two-parameter Weibull wind speed distribution are provided for each of the 12 evenly spaced (30°) wind direction sectors.

Additional wind-related parameters can be derived using the frequency and Weibull parameters and performing a weighted sum over all 12 sectors. For example, to obtain the mean wind speed, we use

$$\bar{u}_{MI} = \sum_{n=1}^{12} f_n A_n \Gamma(1 + 1/\beta_n) \quad (2.1)$$

where the subscript MI stands for microscale, Γ is the Gamma function and n is the sector. A and β are the scale and shape Weibull parameters that are a function of wind direction. Similarly, the Annual Energy Production (\overline{AEP}_{MI}) and Capacity Factor (\overline{CF}_{MI}) can be derived once a wind turbine power curve is chosen.

The NEWA data had to be reformatted to be used with the WIMBY API. The NEWA simulation is run and was previously stored on many tiles due to the size of the data set given the high, 50 m, resolution over all of Europe. The final dataset is 2.3 TiB. This is too large to be stored in a single file, but it would add additional complexity if the server had to find and combine one or more tiles for each area requested by a user. Therefore, another

¹This 10 year period was selected before it better represents the current wind resources

solution needed to be found. Fortunately, the Zarr archive format [3] allows for large data sets to be stored in a directory structure that can be accessed like a single file. It also allows us to use the Rioxarray [4], Xarray [5], and Dask [6] packages to work with the data via chunks, avoiding the saturation of RAM and ensure maximum performance through parallelisation. So, as part of the preparation for the API, the various tiles from NEWA were combined into a single Zarr archive.

2.2 Wind turbine data

Several wind turbine parameters are required to carry out the AEP calculation and optimise the wind turbine locations. These include the height of the rotor, rotor diameter, and the power and thrust curves. The power curve of a wind turbine is a table that indicates how large the electrical power output will be for the turbine at different wind speeds. The thrust is the axial force applied by the wind on the rotor of a wind turbine; it can also be tabulated as a function of the wind speed. Other applications also require noise production but are outside the scope of this report.

The prototype WIMBY Wind Power API presented here has selected four generic wind turbines. These include the three IEA Task 37 Reference wind turbines [7], with the 3.4 MW recommended for onshore and the 10 and 15 MW recommended for offshore. To provide an additional onshore turbine for low-wind conditions, the DTU 3.4 MW LowWind reference turbine [8] is used.

2.3 Exclusion zones

In the context of the WIMBY project, Exclusion Zones (EZ) are areas that prevent and constrain the placement of wind turbines onshore and offshore in Europe. For WIMBY, these zones have been categorised into soft and hard constraints. Hard constraints are areas where, due to legal or physical reasons (e.g., national parks, buildings, or steep cliffs), it is not possible to construct a wind turbine, and therefore, the user is not allowed to do so. The ones used in WIMBY are listed in Table 2.1. Soft constraints include buffer areas around hard constraints determined by law (e.g. distance from the building to reduce noise impact or a protected area where limited building is allowed); the user can decide if they want to follow such guidelines. This report focuses on the hard constraints and describes how they were processed, standardised, and combined to be used as input for the TOPFARM wind farm optimisation tool. The information for soft constraints for all WIMBY countries is available in D2.10. However, how these will be integrated in the WIMBY interactive map depends on feedback from users. Therefore details on these will be provided in D5.2.

Table 2.1: Datasets and their sources used as Hard constraints.

Category	Dataset
Slope	Copernicus DEM GLO-90, 2023 [9]
Urban and Buildings	CORINE Land Cover Polygons, 2018 [10]
Urban and Buildings	World Settlement Footprint, 2019 [11]
Onshore Infrastructure	OpenStreetMap; Selected tags [12]
Hydrology	OpenStreetMap; Glaciers [12]
Hydrology	EU-Hydro River Network Database, 2020 [13]
Protected Areas	Nationally Designated Areas (CDDA) 2023v01 [14]
Protected Areas	UK CDDA 2020v01 [15]
Offshore Infrastructure	OpenStreetMap; Seamarks [12]
Shipping Lanes	EMODnet Human Activities Vessel Density Map, 2023 [16]

To be used in TOPFARM, all exclusion zone layers needed to be represented as polygons. This means that all raster data is converted into polygons, and all the vector data containing Point and Line types is reformatted into Polygons or MultiPolygons by adding a minimum buffer of 1m. Additionally, all layers are reprojected to the ETRS89-extended / LAEA Europe projection (EPSG:3035²), which was used for calculating the NEWA microscale data.

2.3.1 Onshore Exclusion Zones

The onshore exclusion zones include slopes, buildings and urban areas, infrastructure, protected areas, and inland water.

Slope

Slope is a vital exclusion zone as it is too expensive and complete to install turbines in highly complex terrain. For WIMBY, a suitable slope was defined as 36° or less, so all areas with slopes greater than this value should be marked as exclusion zones. To identify these regions, the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) from Copernicus [9] at 90 m of grid spacing was used.

The DEM is first reprojected via `gdalwarp` [17] from WGS84 latitude/longitude projection (EPSG:4326³) to EPSG:3035. Then, the slope is computed by using the `gdaldem slope` tool. Next, the slope dataset was masked

²<https://epsg.io/3035>

³<https://epsg.io/4326>

based on the 36° threshold⁴, with points above this value marked for exclusion. The masked dataset was processed using `gdal_polygonize.py`, keeping only the polygons marking the excluded slopes to create the vector layer.

In a subsequent post-analysis of the generated data, it was found too noisy and contained too many individual vectors. To simplify the data and reduce the noise, a final step was to combine nearby features and drop single-pixel areas. First, all single-pixel areas were dropped from the dataset. Then a 85 m (1-pixel) buffer is applied to every feature, and then a union across all features. This would combine any features that only had 1-pixel of space between them. After the union, the buffer was subtracted, leaving the features with their previous extent minus any pixels merged into the features as part of the union after unionising with the overlapping neighbours. Then, the buffer was subtracted, leaving smoother features and removing the noisy pixels (see Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1: Illustration of the DEM processing: raw slope features after the DEM processing (a), features after a buffer of 85 m was applied (b), the union of the buffered features (c), and unbuffered features as the final step (d).

Buildings and Urban areas

Initially, it was planned only to prevent turbine placement on buildings themselves. Still, after attempting this, it was determined that it would be too difficult to properly handle this in cities due to the number of buildings and their interaction with roads and other structures. The idea was that these areas have so much infrastructure and are so built up that

⁴This value was arbitrarily set based on expert consensus.

it would not be possible, but that trying to get the correct datasets to interact correctly together took a lot of work. Therefore, it was decided that urban areas would be excluded entirely based on land-cover class, and outside of those areas, a building database would be used.

The **CORINE** landcover dataset from 2018 [10] was used to identify urban areas. The classes considered urban for the sake of exclusion zones were.

- Continuous urban fabric (1.1.1)
- Discontinuous urban fabric (1.1.2)
- Industrial or commercial units (1.2.1)
- Construction sites (1.3.3)
- Green urban areas (1.4.1)
- Sport and leisure facilities (1.4.2)

The CORINE land-cover data is provided both as polygons and rasters. We used polygons, so no additional processing was required after filtering the classes.

Building data was taken from the **World Settlement Footprint** dataset [11], derived from Sentinel-2 data and displays settlements from 2019 on a 10m x 10m grid. The WSF is provided as a collection of approximately 2 degree x 2 degree tiles raster tiles. The data is encoded as a single byte with pixel values from 0 to 255. The data were first projected from EPSG:4326 to EPSG:3035 using `gdalwarp`. Then they were converted to a mask using `gdal_calc.py` function, specifying that any value not equal to 0 would become one. This reduced the number of polygons created during the next step, as all values would be marked as either excluded or not. The next step involved converting the settlement footprints in each tile into polygons using the `gdal_polygonize.py` function, followed by dissolving the vector features that were connected into the same polygon using `ogr2ogr`. Then, all the tiles were stitched together. Finally, the settlement data was filtered to remove all features inside a CORINE urban land cover class, as these areas were already excluded.

Infrastructure

In addition to buildings and urban areas, other infrastructure sites were identified as places not to place wind turbines. These sites were identified using the **Open Street Map** (OSM; [12]). The infrastructure sites were selected by subsetting the OSM data using tags. Table 2.2 shows the OSM tags used for creating each infrastructure category.

Table 2.2: OSM tags for different WIMBY infrastructure categories.

Category	OSM Keys	OSM Value
Airport	aeroway	aerodrome
Ferry	route	ferry
Military	landuse	military
Powerlines	power	lines
Radar	tower:type	radar
Railway	railway	rail, narrow
Roads Motorways	highway	motorway, motorway_link, trunk
Roads Primary	highway	primary

The categories listed above were each provided as a separate GeoPackage file in the WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator projection (EPSG:3857⁵). These data consisted mainly of line and point objects. Therefore, they had to be buffered to be converted into polygons. Roadways were buffered by 4 m per lane, while railways were buffered by 2 m, and powerlines were buffered by 42 m. All other objects were buffered by 0.1 m. After buffering, the data layers were concatenated and reprojected to EPSG:3035. All processing was done using GeoPandas [18] in python.

Hydrology

It was determined that turbines would not likely be placed on rivers, lakes, or glaciers, which were included as exclusion zones in WIMBY.

The glacier dataset came from **OSM**, and was selected with the natural key and glacier tag; since it was already polygons, it only needed re-projection.

The remaining data on rivers and wide lakes comes from the **EU-Hydro River Network Database** [13] and is in vector format. It required extra filtering of undesired classes such as river basins (RB), inland water (IW), coastlines (CO), nodes (NO), and transit areas (TR). These were removed because they are already represented in other layers or are not considered an exclusion zone. The processing was performed in Geopandas (Python) by filtering features from the "Class_ID" column that did not match the desired classes.

Protected areas

Protected areas are one of the first exclusion zones that people think of for industrial uses. For hard constraints, we used a subset of protected

⁵<https://epsg.io/3857>

classes.

The **Nationally designated areas (CDDA) 2023 v1** dataset [14] from the European Environment Agency (EEA) was used to identify protected areas in all of Europe except the United Kingdom. Since the UK no longer reports their areas to the EEA, we used their 2020 submission and combined it with the 2023 dataset to create a comprehensive dataset.

The classes Strict Nature Reserve (Ia), Wilderness Area (Ib), National Park (II), Natural Monument or Feature (III) and Habitat/Species Management Area (IV) were identified as hard constraints⁶. GeoPandas was used to filter these polygons and export the data for use in the WIMBY API.

2.3.2 Offshore Exclusion Zones

Offshore exclusion zones only contained two groups: infrastructure and shipping lanes.

Infrastructure

Marine infrastructure that created exclusion areas included fibre optic cables, power lines, oil platforms, buoys, beacons, harbours, and industrial activities. This data, again from **OSM**, was selected using the “Seamarks” tag. Line, multiline and point types of seamarks were included in the selection. For the line and multiline types the values cable_submarine, pipeline_submarine, navigation_line, separation_zone, restricted_area, cable_area, seabed_area, dumping_ground, sand_waves, bridge, marine_farm, precautionary_area, production_area, recommended_traffic_lane, rock, sea_area, separation_boundary, separation_lane, and two-way_route were included. All point values were included in the selection. All offshore features were buffered by 42 m.

Shipping lanes

Shipping lanes are excluded with the assumption that it would be unlikely for wind turbines to be placed in an area that would require many ships to divert around them. This was determined using the **EMODnet Human Activities Vessel Density Map** [16]. This is a raster map with a 1 km × 1 km grid spacing, where every pixel contains the shipping density per year. Three different scenarios were selected to define the exclusion zones. The first one considered areas with a density between 365 (1 ship per day) and 5000 ships per year (13.7 ships per day). The second scenario considered areas with a density between 5001 and 10000 ships per

⁶wind power development could be possible in these areas, social acceptance is low

year (27.4 ships per day), and the third scenario considered only areas with a yearly ship density above 10001 (see Figure 2.2). After binning the data into the three groups, `gdal_polygonize.py` was used to convert the data to polygons for use as exclusion zones.

Figure 2.2: Example of the shipping lanes in the Danish Baltic Sea. Ship densities: low: between 365 and 5000 ships per year (red), middle: between 5001 and 10000 ships per year (blue) and high: above 10001 ships per year (green).

Bathymetry

The dataset is a clipping and reformatting of the EMODnet Bathymetry data [19]. The area clipped extends from 32°N to 72°N in latitude and -14°E to 37°E in longitude. The layer is provided for information only; no exclusion zones are created based on this dataset.

3 MODELS

In this section, we describe the models used for the optimisation of the wind farm layout (TOPFARM; Section 3.1), cost model (Section 3.2), which includes a separate model used to estimate the cost of connection to the power grid (Section 3.3).

3.1 TOPFARM optimization

The EZ layers and NEWA microscale data information are used to perform wind turbine layout optimisation with the open-source tool TOPFARM. The goal is to maximise AEP for a given number of wind turbines and turbine positions while considering some constraints, such as minimum inter-turbine spacing and boundary constraints. For this study, the terrain (or wind farm area) is characterised by non-uniform wind resources from the microscale data, and several exclusion zones are defined from the EZ layers corresponding to land and marine protected areas as well as roads. The wind resource data implicitly includes the changes in wind resources due to elevation and land use change (e.g., top of hills are windier than valleys; winds are reduced around forests). However, the wake calculation and layout optimisation does not include terrain variations.

3.1.1 Read and format EZ layers and NEWA microscale data

The NEWA microscale data are processed to create a PyWake compatible object, and the EZ layers are used to define the exclusion/inclusion zones as boundary constraints. This allows for the representation of non-convex exclusion zones and non-uniform wind resources.

3.1.2 The optimization problem

The software tool uses an optimisation algorithm to return a site's desired wind turbine locations. As previously mentioned, the goal is to maximise the AEP of the wind farm while taking into account wake losses due to wind turbine interaction. TOPFARM uses the information from the EZ layers and the user-provided wind farm area to create its own exclusion and inclusion zones, which are then fed to the workflow as a set of boundary constraints. In addition, a minimum distance of four rotor diameters between turbines is specified and used as a spacing constraint.

In mathematical form, the optimisation problem is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \underset{x,y}{\text{maximize}} && \text{AEP}(x, y) \\
 & \text{subject to} && \sqrt{(x_i - x_j)^2 + (y_i - y_j)^2} \geq S_{\min} \forall i, j : i \neq j \\
 & && C_i \geq 0 \\
 & && x_l \leq x_i \leq x_u \\
 & && y_l \leq y_i \leq y_u
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

where x and y are the turbine coordinate positions (with i and j defining a turbine-specific index), C_i is the exclusion zone distance constraint associated with turbine i (defined in [20]), and AEP is the annual energy production. The positions of the turbines are contained in the area selected for the wind farm. Thus, the turbine positions x and y have lower and upper bounds, represented by the lower horizontal and vertical bounds x_l and y_l , respectively. Similarly, the upper horizontal and vertical bounds are defined as x_u and y_u , respectively. The inter-turbine spacing is represented by S_{\min} , which corresponds, in this case, to 2 turbine diameters in meters.

The AEP is calculated from

$$\text{AEP}(x, y) = 8760 \sum_{j=1}^{N_\theta} \sum_{u=1}^{N_u} \sum_{t=1}^{N_{wt}} P(u_{ijt}) \rho(U_{\infty i}, \theta_{\infty j}), \tag{3.2}$$

where P is power from the power curve, ρ is the site probability mass function, u_{ijt} is the local wind speed, including the effects of the ambient wind speed and the turnings due to the complex landscape and 8760 is the number of hours in a year. The local wind speed is represented by the free stream wind speed (i), turbine location (t) and free stream direction (j). To model the wake effects, we used the NOJ Jensen wake deficit model [21] with a squared sum superposition model, as implemented in the PyWake tool.

3.1.3 Optimization of wind turbine positions

The optimisation algorithm's choice will determine how users will experience the wind farm layout optimization tool in terms of wait time and solution quality. This software tool's main goal is to reduce the optimisation time as much as possible while still yielding accurate results. In this case, we have chosen the site shown in Figure 4.1 to measure the performance of an optimisation algorithm when many exclusion zones are present. The number of inclusion/exclusion zones will impact the simulation time as the optimiser must consider different boundary constraints [20].

As a preliminary study, the heuristics algorithm *smart-start* [22]¹ was used to optimise 50 wind turbines using the sample site shown in Figure 4.1. The algorithm works by sequentially placing wind turbines in the areas with the best wind resources to guess the initial wind farm layout better. It considers the wake effects of the already added wind turbines and the boundary and spacing constraints, ensuring these are not violated. The placement of the turbines is done with a degree of randomness, represented by the parameter r_{pct} , which allows the placement of the next turbine randomly at one of the n best positions. A configuration of $r_{pct} = 0$ places the turbines at the location with the highest AEP, whereas $r_{pct} = 100$ makes the placement completely random, ignoring the AEP value and considering only the spacing and boundary constraints. In addition, the grid resolution defines the number of potential locations (number of points) within the domain. A high-resolution grid will yield better AEP but be computationally costly. On the other hand, a lower-resolution grid will converge faster, which will result in a lower AEP value.

To find the best configuration of *smart-start* that could result in a fast optimisation, a large set of parameters was examined to run the simulations, as seen in Table 3.1. For the wind speeds, a range between 3 and 25 m s⁻¹ is selected, and for the wind direction, a range of 0–360° is chosen. The wind speed and direction are discretised to increase or decrease the number of bins when performing the AEP calculation. A low discretisation yields less wind speeds or wind directions to study, which can affect the simulation time. The random number seed controls random number generation in the algorithm, as explained in [22].

Table 3.1: Grid sweep parameters chosen for the smart-start algorithm

Parameter Name	Grid Sweep Parameters
Randomness percentage [%]	10, 30, 50, 70, 90, 100
Resolution	50, 100, 200, 400
Wind speed discretization [m s ⁻¹]	2, 3, 5, 13
Wind direction discretization [degree]	6, 12, 24, 90, 180, 360
Random seed	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10

The results can be seen in Figure 3.1, where fairly fast optimizations can be obtained with high values of AEP.

¹The Smart-Start algorithm is a heuristic approach based on physics, where wind turbine wake effects guide the decisions to place wind turbines for the initial layout sequentially.

Figure 3.1: Simulation results from the grid sweep optimization performed with the *smart-start* algorithm for the case of 50 wind turbines. The site selected for study corresponds to our DTU Risø campus, which is represented with non-uniform wind resource and exclusion zones.

An optimization of 50 turbines using the *smart-start* algorithm can take from less than 10 seconds to 1 hour depending on the set up. A simulation of 4 seconds can yield an AEP of 256.81 GWh, whereas the maximum AEP was found to be 281.40 GWh for a total workflow time of 5 minutes.

However, from Figure 3.1, it can be seen that there is a possibility for increasing AEP without sacrificing computational time. Suppose we apply a filter to the energy production as in $270 \leq \text{AEP} \leq 280$ GWh. In that case, it is possible to obtain 276 GWh in 8 seconds, which represents a 7.4% increase in energy production for only 4 more seconds of simulation time. The parameters linked to this set-up correspond to:

- $r_{pct} = 10\%$
- grid points = 50
- wind speed = 5 m s^{-1}
- wind direction = 6°

For the wind speed and wind direction, the parameter refers to the discretisation, for the ranges of 3 m s^{-1} to 5 m s^{-1} for the wind speed and 0° to 360° for the wind direction. The domain is discretised with a grid of 50×50 points.

Currently, the tool considers the exclusion zones of a selected area and uses them as boundary constraints within the optimisation problem. The NEWA microscale data gives the wind resource, which PyWake uses to create an object. The site is represented by a dataset containing the x and y coordinates of the domain, the wind direction sectors and heights. For the optimisation, the *smart-start* algorithm was chosen to perform a preliminary study to maximise AEP for the site shown in Figure 4.1. A series of parameters were chosen to explore the algorithm’s performance and suggest a specific setup that can yield very fast solutions to avoid significant user wait times. From the results in Figure 3.1, it can be seen that the algorithm can perform relatively fast optimisations in less than 5 seconds. However, increasing the user wait time results in higher AEP values. The “low” AEPs with large computation times are likely the result of optimizations with large r_{pct} values.

3.2 Levelized Cost of Energy model

The Levelized Cost of Energy, LCOE, is an economic metric used to analyse the cost-benefit relationship of producing energy for different power plants over their entire lifetime. The result of this metric is the unit cost of energy, which for electricity production is in Euro per MWh.

In its most general form, the LCOE can be calculated as

$$\text{LCOE} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^T \frac{C_n}{(1+d)^n}}{\sum_{n=1}^T \frac{E_n}{(1+d)^n}}, \quad (3.3)$$

where n indicates the year of operation, T is the lifetime of the wind turbine and d is the discount rate. The cost and energy produced in the n -th year of operation are C_n and E_n , respectively. When calculating the LCOE, all stages of a technology’s life have to be taken into consideration, for wind turbines this means design and planning, construction, operation and decommissioning as shown in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: Composition and cost of each stage in the whole life cycle of the wind farm after Liu and Life (2023) [23].

Establishing the wanted resolution of the LCOE calculation is important to approximate its scope. At the same time, there is more cost data available for some stages of the wind turbine life cycle. The various stages of a wind turbine's life will be looked at in greater detail to investigate the different costs and how they ought to be modelled. Regional cost differences in these stages are the primary focus.

The Open-source Region-specific ICoe (ORC) model, developed by Max Kellenber from ETH Zürich [24], answers the need for a region-specific wind power plant LCOE model [25]. In the ORC, all of the wind turbine's lifetime stages are modelled separately and combined at the end. Each stage's cost modelling is described in the following sections and subsections. In Figure 3.3, the hierarchy of ORC is visualised, and all components are shown for ease of understanding. Highlighted in yellow are all components that are considered region-specific.

3.2.1 The calculation of LCOE

To answer the need for a region-specific wind power plant LCOE model, the Open-source Region-specific ICoe (ORC) model is presented will be used in the WIMBY API. In ORC all of the wind turbine's lifetime stages are modelled separately and then combined at the end. In Figure 3.3, the hierarchy of ORC is visualized, and all components are shown for ease of understanding. Highlighted in yellow are all components that are considered region-specific. The Electricity Generated is not highlighted because it is already regionalized as input, e.g. it will come from the WIMBY API itself. These various components are detailed in the text that follows.

Figure 3.3: Hierarchy of the ORC model components. Region-specific components are highlighted in yellow. The Electricity Generated is not highlighted because it is already regionalized as input.

Inputs to the ORC model are of two types: technical characteristics of the wind turbine and location-dependent characteristics. Technical characteristics include the turbine's rated power, rotor diameter and hub height. Location-dependent characteristics change with the region in which the turbines are erected. Examples are the AEP, inflation rate, labour wages and transmission charges. In the ORC model, the focus is solely on country values, there we assume that no differences exist on the state- or county level to simplify the modelling and because the data necessary is not public.

3.2.2 LCOE modeling

The ORC model follows the *British Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy* to estimate discounted lifetime cost, thus giving it the name *BEIS*. In Aldersey-Williams and Rubert [26] the equation is given as

$$\text{LCOE}_{\text{BEIS}} = \sum_{n=1}^T \frac{C_n + O_n + V_n}{(1+d)^n} / \sum_{n=1}^T \frac{E_n}{(1+d)^n}, \quad (3.4)$$

On the cost side of the equation, we can see C_n , O_n and V_n , which are capital costs, fixed operating costs and variable operating costs, respec-

tively, all of them about specific year n . Energy generated on the other hand, is represented in the formula as E_n , also dependent on the year n .

The ORC uses a few assumptions for the modelling of LCOE. It is customary that the capital costs C_n are included before the plant starts operating, which means they are not discounted. It is assumed that decommissioning costs occur in the last year of operation; they are included in the variable operating costs for the last year, in ORC's case V_{20} . These assumptions then lead to

$$\text{LCOE}_{\text{BEIS}} = C_n + \sum_{n=1}^T \frac{O_n + V_n}{(1+d)^n} / \sum_{n=1}^T \frac{E_n}{(1+d)^n}. \quad (3.5)$$

This equation gets updated to represent the terminology used throughout the rest of the method such that

$$\text{LCOE}_{\text{BEIS}} = \text{CAPEX} + \sum_{n=1}^T \frac{\text{OPEX} + V_n}{(1+d)^n} / \sum_{n=1}^T \frac{\text{AEP}}{(1+d)^n}, \quad (3.6)$$

where CAPEX are the capital costs, OPEX the annual operational costs, V_n the annual variable costs, d the discount rate and AEP the annual electricity produced. It is assumed that V_n is zero for all years of operation except the final year when it equals the decommissioning cost.

The units of LCOE of the presented model is $\$_{2019}/\text{MWh}$ since models used in the upcoming sections are calculated in 2019 United States dollars. When modelling LCOE, it is crucial not to forget that the discount rate varies from country to country.

3.2.3 Discount rate

The discount rate d is the rate at which the lender (e.g. bank) has to be paid back each year to cover the initial loan [27], in private project investments d is equal to the weighted average cost of capital (WACC). In the ORC, we assume that all the money needed for the project's realisation is borrowed solely from a bank within the same country as the project's realisation because data from private financing is rarely available. The discount rate simplifies to

$$d = \text{WACC} = i_{\text{real}} \times (1 - T), \quad (3.7)$$

where i_{real} is the real interest rate and T is the corporate tax rate.

To further account for differences across countries, we use a more detailed version proposed in [26], which includes the inflation rate.

All data needed to calculate the country-specific discount rate is publicly available and therefore easy to access [28]; the only exceptions are countries with the Euro as currency, as they are omitted. In those cases, we use the current interest rate of the European Central Bank of 4.5 %.

Limited resources are available for predicting the inflation rate, and those available have limited applicability as the global market is quite volatile. Therefore, this model uses the averaged inflation rate over the last 20 years. The inflation rate dataset from the World Bank is used [29].

Lastly, the country-specific corporate tax rate is obtained from the Tax Foundation’s database [30]. With all these values available, the country-specific inflation-adjusted discount rate is computed.

3.2.4 CapEx modeling

The total CapEx is

$$CAPEX = C_{BOS} + C_{Turbine}, \quad (3.8)$$

where C_{BOS} are the cost of Balance-of-System and $C_{Turbine}$ the turbine costs.

3.2.5 Cost of Balance-of-System

Land-based costs of Balance-of-System (BOS)² Engineering (LandBOSSE) is an open-source Excel sheet-based cost model that calculates the Balance-of-System costs C_{BOS} , which include all of the costs associated with the preparation, instalment and erection of the wind turbine [31].

The labour types in the **crew_price** sheet are classified using the international standard classification of occupations that was developed in 1988 by the International Labor Organisation (ILO) [32]. To transform a past value into a present one, the Consumer Price Index (CPI) can be used as follows

$$\$_{2019} = \$_{past} \times \frac{CPI_{2019}}{CPI_{past}}, \quad (3.9)$$

where $\$_{2019}$ is the base currency value, $\$_{past}$ the past currency value, CPI_{2019} the base year’s index and CPI_{past} the past year’s index. Both values of the CPI are obtained from the World Bank CPI dataset [33].

For all cases where data is not available, a wage factor is created

$$\text{wage factor} = \frac{\text{average local wage}}{\text{average US wage}}, \quad (3.10)$$

²term generally used in the context of power engineering and applies to all the supporting components and systems of the power plant which are needed to produce the energy.

that multiplies the values in the Excel sheet to account for the difference in labour costs. The average wages are obtained from ILO's database, more precisely from the Average hourly earnings of employees by sex and occupation dataset [34].

3.2.6 Wind turbine costs

Modelling the cost of the wind turbine C_{Turbine} , is done with the help of the somewhat dated but frequently used *Wind Turbine Design Cost and Scaling* model from NREL [35]. The model uses rated power as input and, depending on that, estimates the cost of each component. In this model, it is assumed that the turbine cost is similar across countries because, in today's global market, the components are made worldwide, making it difficult to compute the actual cost.

The cost of the connection of the wind farm to a substation is modelled separately as described in Section 3.3.

3.2.7 OpEx modeling

The overall annual operating cost can be written as a sum of different cost components

$$\text{OPEX} = C_{\text{land-lease}} + C_{\text{insurance}} + C_{\text{transmission}} + C_{\text{O\&M}}. \quad (3.11)$$

The resulting equation for the total annual cost of land-lease $C_{\text{land-lease}}$ per turbine is

$$C_{\text{land-lease}} = 34.5 \frac{\text{hectare}}{\text{MW}} \times P_r \times C_{\text{land}}, \quad (3.12)$$

where P_r is the rated power of the turbine in MW and C_{land} the rent cost per hectare.

The overall annual insurance cost is

$$C_{\text{insurance}} = \frac{\text{CPI}_{2019}}{\text{CPI}_{2020}} \times P_r, \quad (3.13)$$

where P_r is the rated power, CPI_{2019} and CPI_{2020} are the Consumer Price Indexes in the years 2019 and 2020, respectively.

3.2.8 Transmission costs

In the countries where injection fees³ are available, the annual transmission costs are calculated as follows

$$C_T = \text{AEP} \times \text{injection fee}. \quad (3.14)$$

³Injection charges are paid by all producers connected to the transmission system, and some connected to the distribution network

We use fees and characteristics of European power grids described in the European Union Agency for the Cooperation of Energy Regulators (ACER) [36] report. For countries that did not provide these fees, we use the 2019 average value of 1.1301 [37].

3.2.9 O&M costs

We use the Wind Turbine Design Cost and Scaling Model [35]. The overall annual costs $C_{O\&M}$ consist of the maintenance costs C_M and the replacement cost C_R . Equations for these costs, which were also used by Chen and MacDonald [38], are

$$C_M = 7 \frac{\$}{\text{MWh}} \times \text{AEP}, \quad (3.15)$$

$$C_R = 10.7 \frac{\$}{\text{kW}} \times P_r, \quad (3.16)$$

where P_r the rated power. The costs are adjusted from $\$_{2006}$ to $\$_{2019}$ and a country-specific wage factor is applied. Thus O&M cost are

$$C_{O\&M} = \text{wage factor} \times (C_M + C_R). \quad (3.17)$$

3.2.10 Decommissioning cost modeling

A wind turbine's end-of-life (EOL) is the least researched stage of the lifetime. There also exist options that arise at the EOL, like repowering or extending the lifetime of the turbines [39], but ORC does not model these; it is assumed that the turbine stops operating at the EOL.

The activities modelled in ORC are dismantling the turbine, treating the blades, and treating the tower and the nacelle. The total decommissioning cost is

$$V_{20} = C_{\text{decommissioning}} = C_{\text{dismantling}} + C_{\text{blade-treatment}} + C_{\text{T\&N-treatment}}, \quad (3.18)$$

where $C_{\text{dismantling}}$ is the dismantling cost of the turbine, $C_{\text{blade-treatment}}$ the blade treatment cost and $C_{\text{T\&N-treatment}}$ the tower and nacelle treatment cost. These costs are modelled in Euros and some of these are region-specific. Where data on decommissioning costs is unavailable, it is assumed that the overall revenues and costs equalise each other, which means that for those cases, $C_{\text{decommissioning}}$ is zero.

3.2.11 Dismantling of the turbine

The cost of dismantling the turbine is

$$C_{\text{dismantling}} = C_{\text{transport}} + C_{\text{setup}} + C_{\text{disassembly}}, \quad (3.19)$$

where $C_{\text{transport}}$ is the cost of transporting the crane, C_{setup} the cost of setting up the crane and $C_{\text{disassembly}}$ the cost of disassembling the turbine.

Lastly, the process of taking the turbine components apart takes place. Its cost is

$$C_{\text{disassembly}} = 8 \frac{\text{hours}}{\text{turbine}} \times \left(5 \frac{\text{SEK}}{\text{ton}} \times (K - 200 \text{ tons}) + C_h \right), \quad (3.20)$$

where K is the crane capacity and C_h the hourly cost for the disassembly.

3.2.12 Treatment of the blades

After the turbine is dismantled, individual components must be treated to be put into landfills. The cost for the treatment of blades is

$$C_{\text{blade-treatment}} = C_{\text{severing}} + C_{\text{disposal}}, \quad (3.21)$$

where C_{severing} is the severing cost and C_{disposal} the cost of disposal.

3.3 Grid connection modelling

An onshore wind farm must connect to a nearby transmission substation via overhead cables to deliver the power it produces. More public information on geographic modelling grid connection for wind farms needs to be available. Therefore, the grid connection modelling is developed as an algorithm that roughly estimates the exploratory total grid connection cost based on the distance from the wind farm centroid to the nearest substation⁴. The algorithm can be split into three parts, finding the nearest substation, path planning, and estimating the cable cost. The end product of this section consists of a Python class package that involves the use of several open-source geodata libraries, including GeoPy [40], Shapely [41], Geopandas [18], Fiona [42] and Rasterio [43].

3.3.1 Retrieving nearest substation

Given the centroid coordinates of a wind farm and the country the wind farm is located, the nearby substations in the specified country can be extracted. To ensure the homogeneity of the data used by other WIMBY working groups the substations are sourced from the PyPSA-Eur project [44, 45]. The dataset consists of European high-voltage grid (200 kV to 750 kV) substations constructed using OSM data [46]. It is essential to note that data is missing (or do not have a substation of such size) for 8 countries, which include Andorra, Belarus, Iceland, Liechtenstein, Malta, Monaco, San Marino, and Vatican City. A manual merge of additional substation data will be required if any of these countries are considering

⁴It is assumed that the location of the wind farm is already specified by the user.

the project. For relevant information, all the substations in the dataset are AC substations with a specified voltage level.

The geodesic distance (shortest path between two points on the curvature of the Earth) is used as a first approximation to calculate the distance between each substation and the wind farm. By default, the top 3 substations with minimum geodesic distance are obtained.

Lastly, a relatively accurate geo-referenced plane in units of m is required to calculate the exact distance. As such, Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) projections are utilised [47]. The UTM choice is based on the midpoint between the wind farm and the substation, and all the data are reprojected to the UTM for analysis.

3.3.2 Path planning

In this section, a simplistic model is created for the path-planning process of grid connection. A "step-wise" algorithm is implemented to keep the run-time at its minimum. For a given max spacing radius and tower height for transmission cables (by default 500 m and 50 m), the following point is determined to be the one with the closest distance to the substation. Note that the max spacing radius defines the maximal 2D spacing between two neighbouring towers along the transmission line (i.e. not accounting for elevation). As such, a straight line with a relative equal spacing is created. Two exceptions will alter this path.

The first factor relates to the cable violating the actual height from the digital elevation model (DEM), especially around mountainous regions. Between two neighbouring towers, the cable is modelled as a straight line segment from one tower top to another tower top. This line segment needs to be strictly higher than the ground. If this condition is violated, it is adjusted by decreasing the spacing until it clears the violation.

The second, more complex factor is the violation of exclusion zones. The current exclusion zone layer is sourced from the European Environment Agency (EEA) protected areas database [48]. The database includes the national designated areas for the protected sites in 38 European countries. Further effort must be made to include additional exclusion zones concerning overhead cable infrastructure, such as airports, roads, and households. To avoid time-consuming global search algorithms, the violation towards exclusion zones is considered a penalty towards the total overall cost. The penalty is implemented as a post-processing procedure that takes the points under violation and creates an arc with the violated distance as the diameter. The side with the least violation will be chosen for visualisation purposes, as shown in Figure 3.4. Exclusion zones are for now independent of those used for the WIMBY API, but

will be generalized once the LCOE model is integrated.

3.3.3 Estimating total cable costs

The cable cost is estimated post path planning based on a 2024 technical report by Mid-continent Independent System Operator (MISO), a Transmission System Operator in the USA [49]. The report includes exploratory estimate costs of single and double circuit AC transmission lines in \$₂₀₂₄/miles at various voltage levels (69 kV - 745 kV) across 15 states in the United States. This technical report is comprehensive at a broad level, including the tower and associated project costs. The costs are translated from \$₂₀₂₄/miles to \$₂₀₁₉/ km using world bank Consumer Price Index (CPI) data [50]. To differentiate between different European countries, labour costs are sourced from the International Labour Organization (ILO) and computed as a ratio to the United States labour cost [51]. Considering a rough estimate that labour costs account for $\gamma = 50\%$ of the entire project, the estimated exploratory cable cost C_{cable} in \$₂₀₁₉/ km at a given voltage (from substation properties) can be written as:

$$C_{cable} = \gamma C_{MISO} \frac{\text{Labour Cost EU country}}{\text{Labour Cost US}} + (1 - \gamma) C_{MISO} \quad (3.22)$$

An example for AC costs at various voltages depending on different European countries can be seen in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2: Single Circuit AC exploratory costs across various European countries at different voltage levels. All numbers are in million \$₂₀₁₉/ km

Country/Voltage [kV]	69	115	138	161	230	345	500	765
Albania	0.43	0.48	0.50	0.51	0.54	0.87	1.09	1.36
Austria	0.72	0.80	0.84	0.86	0.91	1.46	1.82	2.29
Belgium	0.71	0.80	0.84	0.86	0.91	1.46	1.82	2.29
Bosnia and Herzegovina	0.44	0.49	0.52	0.53	0.56	0.91	1.13	1.42
Bulgaria	0.44	0.49	0.51	0.53	0.56	0.90	1.12	1.41
Croatia	0.49	0.55	0.58	0.59	0.63	1.01	1.26	1.58
Czechia	0.49	0.54	0.57	0.58	0.62	1.00	1.24	1.56
Denmark	0.91	1.02	1.07	1.10	1.16	1.87	2.33	2.93
Estonia	0.50	0.56	0.58	0.60	0.64	1.02	1.28	1.60
Finland	0.90	1.00	1.05	1.08	1.15	1.84	2.30	2.89
France	0.61	0.68	0.71	0.73	0.78	1.25	1.56	1.96
Germany	0.55	0.62	0.65	0.66	0.71	1.13	1.41	1.78
Greece	0.49	0.55	0.57	0.59	0.63	1.00	1.25	1.57
Hungary	0.50	0.55	0.58	0.59	0.63	1.01	1.26	1.59
Ireland	0.66	0.74	0.77	0.79	0.84	1.35	1.69	2.12
Italy	0.55	0.62	0.65	0.67	0.71	1.13	1.42	1.78
Latvia	0.48	0.53	0.56	0.57	0.61	0.98	1.22	1.54
Lithuania	0.46	0.52	0.54	0.55	0.59	0.95	1.18	1.48
Luxembourg	0.79	0.88	0.92	0.95	1.01	1.61	2.01	2.53
Moldova	0.41	0.45	0.48	0.49	0.52	0.83	1.04	1.30
Montenegro	0.47	0.52	0.54	0.56	0.59	0.95	1.19	1.49
Netherlands	0.70	0.78	0.82	0.84	0.89	1.43	1.78	2.24
North Macedonia	0.44	0.50	0.52	0.53	0.57	0.91	1.13	1.42
Norway	0.90	1.01	1.06	1.08	1.15	1.85	2.30	2.90
Poland	0.41	0.46	0.48	0.50	0.53	0.84	1.05	1.32
Portugal	0.49	0.54	0.57	0.59	0.62	1.00	1.24	1.56
Romania	0.46	0.51	0.54	0.55	0.59	0.94	1.17	1.47
Serbia	0.45	0.50	0.52	0.53	0.57	0.91	1.14	1.43
Slovakia	0.47	0.53	0.55	0.56	0.60	0.96	1.20	1.51
Slovenia	0.55	0.61	0.64	0.66	0.70	1.13	1.40	1.77
Spain	0.65	0.73	0.76	0.78	0.83	1.34	1.67	2.10
Sweden	0.70	0.79	0.82	0.85	0.90	1.44	1.80	2.26
Switzerland	1.05	1.18	1.23	1.26	1.34	2.15	2.69	3.38
Ukraine	0.40	0.44	0.46	0.48	0.51	0.81	1.01	1.27
United Kingdom	0.65	0.72	0.76	0.78	0.83	1.32	1.65	2.07

A final penalty is added if the slope is too high at the next point where a tower should be built. No penalty is incurred for a point less than 5°. For a point that is above 45°, a penalty of 100 % is added to that segment cost. For in-between values, a linear percentage increase penalty from 5 % to 45 % is added.

3.3.4 Example

A random coordinate is taken in Bulgaria for the example given in Figure 3.4 and Figure 3.5. The grid connection solution is a 220 kV substation in the south-west corner, totalling an estimated route distance of 18.8

km and an estimated cost of 11.5 million \$₂₀₁₉ for a single circuit or 18.28 million \$₂₀₁₉ for a double circuit AC transmission.

Figure 3.4: A visualisation of the path from a random wind farm in Bulgaria to its nearest substation. The DEM is plotted as a background

Figure 3.5: Visualisation of the elevation from a random wind farm in Bulgaria to its nearest substation.

The overall run-time of the algorithm itself is light computationally, but the overall program runs in 5 to 15 seconds. The increase in time is attributed to complex geometries in the exclusion zone layer.

4 The WIMBY API

The WIMBY API is an HTTP API developed using the FastAPI python library [52]. As an HTTP API, it uses HTTP verbs to control the meaning of different requests to send and receive data. The primary purpose of the API is to provide a calculation engine for the WIMBY interactive map, which is developed as part of WP5. The API can be grouped into two parts; the first part uses the TOPFARM model (described in section 3.1 to optimise the layout of a turbine to provide the highest estimated annual energy production (AEP). The second part calculates the possible social and environmental impacts¹ of installing turbines at the locations determined by the optimisation.

The application is built within a Docker container, isolating all the application code and dependencies in a single image to ensure quick and reliable behaviour between different computer environments. The container can be used during development on a user's local machine and then deployed to a web server, where users can perform their desired analysis through the available endpoints.

4.1 The WIMBY Wind Power Tool

The Wind Power Tool is built to be deployed on a web server and provides an API interface to calculate the locations of turbines within a wind farm boundary. The user will provide a location of interest (e.g., a polygon) and necessary wind farm design criteria, including the turbine type, hub height, and the number of turbines. The optimisation tool will run and provide the wind turbines' locations to maximise the wind farm's energy production. The result is the geographic location of each turbine and the estimated AEP for the entire wind farm.

¹The noise, LCA and shadow flicker models are integrated into the WIMBY API. The rest will be integrated as part of the work in the WIMBY interactive map - D5.2

Figure 4.1: Flow diagram of the main components of the WIMBY wind power tool.

Figure 4.1 is the flow diagram of the software tool, where the wind resources (upper left), exclusion zones (bottom left) and wind turbine data are combined to create the optimised wind farm layout (right). The effect of the terrain and land use on the wind is implicitly included in the input wind resource data. This chapter describes the methods used in these three phases.

4.1.1 Endpoints

The WIMBY API has three endpoints that are used to run the wind power tool:

upload_polygon: takes a user-provided GeoJSON² polygon. Calculates a hash of the GeoJSON, reads it with GeoPandas, and saves the result as a GeoPackage. The hash value is returned as an ID for future API calls.

preproc_inputs: Takes the ID from upload_polygon, and performs the spatial calculations over the wind resources and exclusion zone data (described in Sections 2.1, and 2.3 respectively). This endpoint creates two intermediate files from the exclusion zone data (EZ) prepared in 2.3, and the microscale wind climate (NEWA) described

²format for encoding a variety of geographic data structures

in 2.1. The files are created by clipping the data to the selected region (see Figure 4.2) and converting it to a format that works well with TOPFARM, which is clipped in the requested area.

Figure 4.2: Clipping to the exclusion zones. Source [53].

The EZ data is prepared for TOPFARM by looping over several files representing the different types of EZs and clipping each one using GeoPandas. Then, the clipped data is joined using a union before being saved as a GeoPackage.

The NEWA data is clipped to a bounding box of the selected area using RioXarray. The resulting dataset is converted to a PyWake [54] XRSite object and saved to disk as a netCDF file using that object save function.

The endpoint returns the polygon ID, which can be used to identify the two datasets.

site_turbines: Takes polygon ID as the IDs of the two datasets created from the **preproc_inputs** endpoint and the wind turbine characteristics (number of turbines and turbine type) as input. These are used to run the TOPFARM optimisation routine and determine the optimal locations for wind turbines in the requested area. The output is a JSON object that provides the location of each turbine, turbine metadata that contains the name, hub height, diameter and rated power in megawatts, and the wind farm's energy as AEP in GWh and the capacity factor.

4.2 Impact Models

Currently, three impact models are part of the API: a Noise model, a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) Model and a Shadow Flicker model. They are run using the results from the optimisation and can be accessed through the following endpoints:

run_noise_model The noise model uses the 24x12 table to determine the wind climate around each turbine location. The result is a vector map of polygons showing the area affected by critical decibel

levels above (35, 40, 45, 50, 55, and 60 db). The polygon map is returned as a GeoJSON.

life_cycle_assessment: The LCA model is run in the API by first converting the units of the optimisation approach to those needed by the LCA model and then running the model. The results are a few statistics, such as the turbine impact factor, number of turbines, wind farm impact factor, and normalised wind farm impact factor.

shadow_flicker/run: The shadow flicker model, like the noise model, relies on the 24 x 12 table and the optimisation results. The shadow flicker model has several hard-coded parameters that can be used to run it on the server. These include a maximum shadow length of 4,000, an output resolution of 90, and cut-in and cut-out speeds of 2 and 25 m s⁻¹, respectively. The model is run for a single representative year (2023), with the parameters $r_{day} = 14$, $r_{hour} = 1$, and $r_{minutes} = 4$. The result of the shadow flicker model is a GeoTiff showing the number of hours of the day that a location would be affected by shadow flicker, which is saved to disk. The endpoint returns the ID of the model run, which can be used to get the model result with the following endpoint.

shadow_flicker/{polygon_id}.tif: This endpoint returns the GeoTiff for the selected polygon.

5 CONCLUSIONS

We summarise the activities related to creating the WIMBY Wind Power API, which merges wind resources, farm boundaries, and turbine details to evaluate the energy potential of wind farms across Europe. The tool unifies DTU's previously separate models to generate an optimised wind farm layout using publicly available datasets and user-defined configurations.

The WIMBY Wind Power API is designed for deployment on a web server. It provides an API interface to determine turbine placements within a user-defined wind farm boundary. Users input a location of interest (e.g., a polygon) and essential design parameters (number and type of turbines). The optimisation tool processes this information and returns the optimal turbine locations to enhance the wind farm's energy output. It also details the geographical placements of each turbine and the Annual Energy Production (AEP) for the entire wind farm.

The prototype of the WIMBY Wind Power API was completed on time. The noise and shadow flicker models have already been incorporated into the API. Until the WIMBY interactive map (D5.2) is released, ongoing efforts will include debugging, performance optimisation, and integrating additional models developed by other partners.

REFERENCES

- [1] Andrea N Hahmann, Neil N. Davis, and Nicolas D. Gonzalez Alonso De Linaje. *WIMBY Deliverable D1.1 Report: Description of the wind resources API*. Tech. rep. DTU Wind, 2024. URL: <https://wimby.eu/resource/d1-1-wind-resources-api/>.
- [2] Consortium NEWA. *Web interface to the New European Wind Atlas*. 2018. URL: <https://map.neweuropeanwindatlas.eu/> (visited on 12/05/2023).
- [3] Alistair Miles et al. *zarr-developers/zarr-python: v3.0.0-beta.2*. Version v3.0.0-beta.2. Nov. 2024. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14165945. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14165945>.
- [4] Alan D. Snow et al. *corteva/rioxarray: 0.15.0 Release (0.15.0)*. 2023. DOI: Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8247542>. URL: <https://corteva.github.io/rioxarray/stable/index.html> (visited on 12/13/2023).
- [5] *Xarray documentation*. URL: <https://docs.xarray.dev/en/stable/> (visited on 12/12/2023).
- [6] *Dask – Scale the Python tools you love*. URL: <https://www.dask.org/> (visited on 12/13/2023).
- [7] Pietro Bortolotti et al. *IEA Wind Task 37 on Systems Engineering in Wind Energy – WP2.1 Reference Wind Turbines*. Tech. rep. International Energy Agency, 2019. URL: <https://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy19osti/73492.pdf>.
- [8] H. Aa Madsen et al. “Initial performance and load analysis of the LowWind turbine in comparison with a conventional turbine”. In: *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 1618.3 (2020), p. 032011. DOI: 10.1088/1742-6596/1618/3/032011. URL: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1618/3/032011>.
- [9] *Copernicus DEM – Global and European Digital Elevation Model*. <https://doi.org/10.5270/ESA-c5d3d65>. Accessed through the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem. 2020.
- [10] *CORINE Land Cover 2018 (vector), Europe, 6-yearly*. <https://doi.org/10.2909/71c95a07-e296-44fc-b22b-415f42acfd0>. Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, European Environment Agency. 2020.
- [11] Mattia Marconcini et al. *World Settlement Footprint (WSF) 2019 – Sentinel-1/2 – Global*. <https://doi.org/10.15489/twg5xsnquw84>. German Aerospace Center (DLR), Copernicus data, licensed under CC-BY-4.0. 2021.
- [12] OpenStreetMap contributors. 2024.
- [13] *EU-Hydro River Network Database 2006–2012, Europe – version 1.3*. <https://doi.org/10.2909/393359a7-7ebd-4a52-80ac-1a18d5f3db9c>. Coperni-

- cus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS), European Environment Agency (EEA). 2020.
- [14] European Environment Agency. *Nationally designated areas for public access (vector data) - version 21, Jun. 2023*. 2023. URL: <https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/srv/api/records/ef77dd7b-e5d0-4b93-81e1-f721b91ec9fe>.
- [15] European Environment Agency. *Nationally designated areas (CDDA) for public access - version 18, May 2020*. 2020. URL: <https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/srv/api/records/b07cd829-47da-416c-83f5-9dc952191bfc>.
- [16] *EMODnet Human Activities, Vessel Density Map (2017-2023)*. <https://ows.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/geonetwork/srv/api/records/0f2f3ff1-30ef-49e1-96e7-8ca78d58a07c>. European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet), licensed under CC BY 4.0. 2023.
- [17] GDAL/OGR contributors. *GDAL/OGR Geospatial Data Abstraction software Library*. Open Source Geospatial Foundation. 2024. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5884351. URL: <https://gdal.org>.
- [18] *GeoPandas*. URL: <https://geopandas.org/en/stable/> (visited on 12/12/2023).
- [19] *EMODnet Digital Bathymetry (DTM) 2022*. <https://sextant.ifremer.fr/record/ff3aff8a-cff1-44a3-a2c8-1910bf109f85/>. European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet), licensed under CC BY 4.0. 2022.
- [20] J. Criado Risco et al. "Gradient-based wind farm layout optimization with inclusion and exclusion zones". In: *Wind Energy Science* 9.3 (2024), pp. 585–600. DOI: 10.5194/wes-9-585-2024. URL: <https://wes.copernicus.org/articles/9/585/2024/>.
- [21] N. O. Jensen. *A note on wind generator interaction*. Tech. rep. 2411. 1983. URL: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:55059791>.
- [22] R. Valotta Rodrigues et al. "Speeding up large-wind-farm layout optimization using gradients, parallelization, and a heuristic algorithm for the initial layout". In: *Wind Energy Science* 9.2 (2024), pp. 321–341. DOI: 10.5194/wes-9-321-2024. URL: <https://wes.copernicus.org/articles/9/321/2024/>.
- [23] Junbo Liu et al. "Life cycle cost modelling and economic analysis of wind power: A state of art review". In: *Energy Conversion and Management* 277 (Feb. 1, 2023), p. 116628. ISSN: 0196-8904. DOI: 10.1016/j.enconman.2022.116628. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0196890422014066> (visited on 03/06/2024).
- [24] Max Kellenber. "Region-specific wind power plant LCOE model". Bachelor Thesis. Swiss Federal Institute of Technology (ETH), Zürich, 2024.
- [25] Max Kellenberger. *ORC (Open-source Regional-specific LCOE model)*. 2024. URL: <https://github.com/mkellenbe/ORC> (visited on 12/06/2024).

- [26] J. Aldersey-Williams and T. Rubert. "Levelised cost of energy – A theoretical justification and critical assessment". In: *Energy Policy* 124 (Jan. 1, 2019), pp. 169–179. ISSN: 0301-4215. DOI: 10.1016/j.enpol.2018.10.004. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301421518306645> (visited on 03/07/2024).
- [27] L. D. Danny Harvey. "Clarifications of and improvements to the equations used to calculate the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE), and comments on the weighted average cost of capital (WACC)". In: *Energy* 207 (Sept. 15, 2020), p. 118340. ISSN: 0360-5442. DOI: 10.1016/j.energy.2020.118340. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S036054422031447X> (visited on 03/15/2024).
- [28] World Bank. *Real interest rate (%)*. URL: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/FR.INR.RINR>.
- [29] Jongrim Ha, M Ayhan Kose, and Franziska Ohnsorge. "One-Stop Source: A Global Database of Inflation". In: *Journal of International Money and Finance*. 102896th ser. 137 (2023).
- [30] Cristina Enache. *Corporate Tax Rates Around the World, 2022*. Dec. 13, 2022. URL: <https://taxfoundation.org/data/all/global/corporate-tax-rates-by-country-2022/> (visited on 04/26/2024).
- [31] Annika Eberle et al. "NREL's Balance-of-System Cost Model for Land-Based Wind". In: (2019). URL: <https://research-hub.nrel.gov/en/publications/nrelaposs-balance-of-system-cost-model-for-land-based-wind> (visited on 03/15/2024).
- [32] ILO. "International standard classification of occupations – (ISCO-88). 1988 edition". In: (Jan. 8, 1991). ISSN: 9221148327.
- [33] World Bank. *Consumer price index (2010 = 100)*. URL: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/FP.CPI.TOTL>.
- [34] ILO. *Average hourly earnings of employees by sex and occupation – Annual*. URL: https://rshiny.ilo.org/dataexplorer49/?lang=en&id=EAR_4HRL_SEX_OCU_CUR_NB_A.
- [35] L. Fingersh, M. Hand, and A. Laxson. *Wind Turbine Design Cost and Scaling Model*. NREL/TP-500-40566. Dec. 1, 2006, NREL/TP-500-40566. DOI: 10.2172/897434. URL: <http://www.osti.gov/servlets/purl/897434-Feoadi/> (visited on 03/04/2024).
- [36] ACER. *Report on Electricity Transmission and Distribution Tariff Methodologies in Europe*. www.acer.europa.eu. Jan. 2023. URL: <https://www.acer.europa.eu/news-and-events/news/acer-publishes-its-latest-report-how-electricity-network-tariffs-are-set-europe> (visited on 04/24/2024).
- [37] *Euro (EUR) To US Dollar (USD) Exchange Rate History for 2017*. URL: <https://www.exchange-rates.org/exchange-rate-history/eur-usd-2017> (visited on 05/06/2024).

- [38] Le Chen et al. "Modeling noise and lease soft costs improves wind farm design and cost-of-energy predictions". In: *Renewable Energy* 97 (Nov. 1, 2016), pp. 849–859. ISSN: 0960-1481. DOI: 10.1016/j.renene.2016.05.045. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0960148116304566> (visited on 03/19/2024).
- [39] Lisa Ziegler et al. "Lifetime extension of onshore wind turbines: A review covering Germany, Spain, Denmark, and the UK". In: *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 82 (Feb. 1, 2018), pp. 1261–1271. ISSN: 1364-0321. DOI: 10.1016/j.rser.2017.09.100. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032117313503> (visited on 03/07/2024).
- [40] *Welcome to GeoPy's documentation!*. URL: <https://geopy.readthedocs.io/en/stable/> (visited on 10/01/2024).
- [41] *The Shapely User Manual*. URL: <https://shapely.readthedocs.io/en/stable/manual.html> (visited on 10/01/2024).
- [42] *Fiona*. URL: <https://pypi.org/project/fiona/> (visited on 10/01/2024).
- [43] *Rasterio: access to geospatial raster data*. URL: <https://rasterio.readthedocs.io/en/stable/index.html> (visited on 12/12/2023).
- [44] Jonas Hoersch et al. "PyPSA-Eur: An open optimisation model of the European transmission system". In: *Energy Strategy Reviews* 22 (2018), pp. 207–215. DOI: 10.1016/j.esr.2018.08.012. eprint: 1806.01613.
- [45] *PyPSA-Eur. A Sector-Coupled Open Optimisation Model of the European Energy System*. 2024. URL: <https://pypsa-eur.readthedocs.io/en/latest/> (visited on 12/20/2024).
- [46] Bobby Xiong et al. *Prebuilt Electricity Network for PyPSA-Eur based on OpenStreetMap Data*. Tech. rep. Technische Universität Berlin, 2024.
- [47] 21. *The UTM Grid and Transverse Mercator Projection*. URL: https://www.e-education.psu.edu/natureofgeoinfo/c2_p22.html (visited on 10/01/2024).
- [48] *European protected sites*. URL: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/maps-and-charts/european-protected-areas-1?activeTab=570bee2d-1316-48cf-adde-4b640f92119b> (visited on 10/01/2024).
- [49] *Transmission Cost Estimation Guide For MTEP24*. URL: <https://cdn.misoenergy.org/MISO%20Transmission%20Cost%20Estimation%20Guide%20for%20MTEP24337433.pdf> (visited on 10/01/2024).
- [50] *Consumer price index (2010 = 100)*. URL: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/FP.CPI.TOTL> (visited on 10/01/2024).
- [51] *ILOSTAT data explorer: Average hourly earnings of employees by sex and occupation - Annual*. URL: https://rshiny.ilo.org/dataexplorer49/?lang=en&id=EAR_4HRL_SEX_OCU_CUR_NB_A (visited on 10/01/2024).

- [52] Sebastián Ramírez. *FastAPI*. If you use this software, please cite it using the metadata from this file. 2024. URL: <https://fastapi.tiangolo.com>.
- [53] GIS Geography. *Clip tool in GIS*. URL: <https://gisgeography.com/clip-tool-gis/> (visited on 12/03/2023).
- [54] Mads M. Pedersen and Pierre-Elouan Réthoré. *PyWake 2.5.0: An open-source wind farm simulation tool*. Publisher: DTU Wind, Technical University of Denmark. Feb. 2023. URL: <https://gitlab.windenergy.dtu.dk/TOPFARM/PyWake>.

